

Impact of Organized Educational Programs on Mothers' Knowledge of Preventing Mishaps at Home for Their Children in Urban Bangalore

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Abstract

In a quasi-experimental study, sixty respondents from Kerendahalli answered questions about how organized strategies affect parents' perceptions of keeping their children safe at home. The non-probability purposive sampling method was used to choose the study's sample. To gather information from the participants, the researcher has created a systematic interview schedule. Graphs and charts were used to analyze and visualize the gathered data using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Of the sixty people, fourteen (23.3%) did not know enough to avoid mishaps during the pretest. Prior to intervention, there was a dearth of knowledge regarding the prevention of home accidents among mothers' children; the percentage of mothers who had acceptable and good knowledge on the topic was only 31 (51.7) and 15 (25%), respectively. Nevertheless, according to the post-test results, out of 60 respondents, 21 (35%) had moderate knowledge and 39 (65%) had high knowledge about how to prevent accidents at home for kids. The mean score for total knowledge on the pretest was 16.32 with a standard deviation of 6.62, while the posttest resulted in a mean of 31.02 with a standard deviation of 4.99. It proves the effectiveness of the intervention. Mothers' age, profession, education, and degree of awareness about preventing accidents in children are highly correlated. The study's findings support that. Using a coordinated teaching approach, mothers' awareness of how to avoid accidents at home with their children was enhanced.

Introduction

Children frequently escape accidents with long-term physical or mental impairments that limit their activities. Open wounds, poisoning, and head traumas are the most often reported unintentional injuries. Treating accident-related injuries requires a significant financial investment for families and health care institutions, even in cases when the consequences are transient [1].

Although there is research on accidental domestic accidents involving children in Oman, no study to date has examined the frequency of domestic accidents involving children of different ages, and the nature and consequences of the injuries [2]. Thus, the purpose of

this study was to ascertain how frequently children were brought to the emergency room of a third university hospital in Oman following unintentional household incidents during a six-month period [3]. The study details the most frequent reasons why children in various age groups have accidents at home, along with the extent and results of injuries [4].

According to the World Health Organization, an accident is an unexpected and unexpected event that results in physical or mental injury. Children who are less aware of the danger are among the most at risk, which can be explained by the fact that their neuromas and their cognitive, physical, socio-psychological and sensory abilities are still developing. The injuries are not

More Information

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intentional. About 90% of accidents can be avoided by taking safety precautions [5].

Community health nurses can assist prevent accidents affecting infants and children by safeguarding the infants and children under their care, giving parents wise advice on accident prevention, and setting a good example for safe behavior. Nurses can assist avert accidents in hospitals or the community by advising parents to keep a watchful eye on their children [6].

To have a more thorough understanding of how structured educational initiatives improve mothers' knowledge of child safety and accident prevention, a systematic examination of the "Impact of Organized Educational Programs on Mothers' Knowledge of Child Safety in Urban Bangalore" research project has been undertaken [7]. Prior research has recognized the value of teaching caregivers about child safety, but it frequently lacked a targeted investigation of structured initiatives aimed primarily at urban women [8].

The purpose of this research on the "Impact of Organized Educational Programs on Mothers' Knowledge of Child Safety in Urban Bangalore" is to systematically examine how structured educational interventions enhance mothers' understanding of child safety and accident prevention. Previous studies have acknowledged the importance of educating caregivers about child safety; however, they often lack a focused exploration of organized programs specifically targeting mothers in urban environments [9].

By evaluating the efficiency of such educational activities in raising mothers' awareness, knowledge, and practical skills, this study seeks to close this knowledge gap. The study aims to clarify how organized education can result in improved child safety outcomes by examining the association between participation in these programs and increases in safety knowledge [10]. In the end, this research aims to contribute to the larger objective of improving child welfare and lowering home-related accidents by providing information for the creation of focused educational initiatives and legislation that meet the particular safety difficulties encountered by metropolitan Bangalore households.

Here the researcher aim to Analyze the impact of an organized educational approach on mothers knowledge of preventing mishaps at home for their children therefore this study clarifies and proving about educational intervention play a major role in enhancing the knowledge of the mother in prevention of accidents among the children's at home.

Hypotheses H1 Mothers who participate in organized educational programs will elicit a significantly higher knowledge of child safety compared to those who do not participate and Mothers' increased awareness of child safety will result in a discernible decline in child accidents in Bangalore's cities that happen at home.

Methods

Study Design and Participants

A quasi-experimental study was conducted. The knowledge score of the respondents who received the intervention towards safety measures after the Education were higher than before the education. This investigation was carried out in Keregundahelli urban part of North Bangalore (study setting) Karnataka, India.

Population The moms who live in urban Bangalore and have children between the ages of 0 and 12 are the target demographic for this study. The reason this age range was chosen is that it includes critical developmental phases where safety teaching is very important.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

Sample Size: Approximately sixty moms be included into the sample so as to ensure statistical significance and accurate representation.

Sampling Technique: To guarantee that different socioeconomic origins are represented and to enable a thorough analysis of knowledge discrepancies, a simple random selection method will be employed.

The inclusion criteria was follows as the mothers who have children age group between 0-5 yrs., mothers who were interest to participate in this study and the mother who were available at the time of data collection. Variables under this this study were Programs for Organized Education (structured interventions focused on child safety) are an independent variable. Mothers' knowledge, comprehension, and practical skills in relation to averting mishaps at home are the dependent variable.

The sample was calculated based on means with standard deviation ($3.1+1.7= 4.8$) of the pilot study finding assuming that 80% power at 0.05 level of significance and 2.6 clinical differences $N=z \{z1+z1-b/d\} s n= 2.6$ this result shows that 60 sample needed to conduct this present study so the mothers were selected based on inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Research Design

The researcher used a quasi-experimental one group pretest and posttest design for this study, and the dependent variables in knowledge of home accident prevention among children between the ages of 0 and 6 are the educational approach and knowledge of home accident prevention among children. The term "extraneous variables" refers to variables that are present in a study setting and have the potential to skew the results by functioning as unintended independent variables. In this study, the mother's age, occupation, and educational level are considered extraneous variables.

Construction of the Tool and Teaching Approach

Objectives of the study and the researcher has to answer for following question

- To evaluate mothers' understanding on preventing Mishaps at home for their kids through a pre-test
- To create and implement an educational approach aimed at educating mothers on how to prevent Mishaps at home for their children.
- To evaluate mothers' knowledge on preventing Mishaps this topic through a post-test.
- To evaluate the effectiveness of regarding preventing Mishaps at Home for their Children by pretest and post test score
- To determine the association with posttest knowledge score and selected demographic variables regarding preventing Mishaps at Home for their Children

Under the direction of subject matter specialists and based on an assessment of relevant literature, the research tool and teaching module were created. Five experts evaluated the tool's content validity: one pediatrician and four professionals in the field of child health nursing. The required recommendations and adjustments were included in the tool's final preparation. The test-retest approach was used to evaluate the tool's reliability (r = 0.08). Results demonstrated the tool's dependability.

On the basis of Mother Knowledge level, educational programme regarding prevention of home accidents among children's were developed by using following structure like Development of the course out line .development of criteria rating scale, preparation of the learning programme in that the researcher has given more important to meaning and definition of home accidents ,Type and causes of home accidents ,first aid measures and preventive measures

Ethical Consideration

The current study was carried out in our chosen village with permission from the Primary Health Center's medical officer. Before the study began, the

participants gave their consent in order to safeguard their legal right to participate in research. The mothers took part in the program voluntarily and were free to leave at any moment.

Data Collection

Formal permission was obtained from the concern authority to conduct the study. 60 samples were chosen as per laid down criteria consent was obtained from the each subjects after giving assurance of confidentiality, pretest was given on day one followed by educational intervention and on the day seventh posttest was taken with unchanged tools

Data Analysis

The collected data was coded and transformed to master sheets for analysis and analyses result was portrait in the form of charts The information was arranged, tallied, condensed, and subjected to both inferential and descriptive statistical analysis. The "t" test was used to do the analysis. Using the χ^2 (chi-square) test, the relationship between the chosen demographic variables and knowledge was examined and deduced.

Results

The following headings describe how the data from this study were arranged, collated, analyzed, and interpreted using statistical tables and graphs. Section A has little sociodemographic data. Section B: Knowledge level of mothers. This table shows the overall distribution of pretest knowledge scores of samples about accident prevention as well as the distribution of scores by domain. The comparison of mothers' pretest knowledge scores regarding preventing home accidents with specific sociodemographic variables, the domain-wise distribution of the samples' posttest knowledge scores regarding accident prevention, and the overall distribution of the samples' posttest knowledge scores regarding accident prevention Table shows the sociodemographic variables.

Table 1: Sociodemographic Variables

Sl.no	Sociodemographic variables	No of subjects	Percentage
1	Age group		
	20-24 years	19	31.60
	25-30 years	21	35.00
	31-35 years	16	26.70
	Above 36 years	04	06.70
2	Education		
	Illiterate	14	23.30
	literate	16	26.70
	Graduate	20	33.30
	Post graduate	10	18.30
3	Occupation		
	Home maker	13	21.70
	Daily wages	24	40.00
	Self employed	12	20.00

	Skilled worker	11	18.30
4	Religions		
	Hindu	09	15.00
	Muslim	29	48.30
	Christian	22	36.70
5	Type of Family		
	Nuclear	40	66.6
	Extended	20	33.3
6	Source of Previous Knowledge		
	Television	19	31.67
	News paper	09	15
	Health workers	18	30
	From family members	14	23.33
7	No. of children in the family		
	One	22	36.67
	Two	21	35
	More than two	17	28.3

Figure 1: Demographic Variables

In regards with age of the sample out of 60 respondents 19 (31.6%) of mothers were in the age group between 20 -24 years and 21% of the respondents were in the age group between 25-30years and 16(26.7%) mothers were in the age group between 31-35 years and 4 (6.7) mother were in the age group of above 36 years ,Here the researcher is concluding that majority of the

respondents who took part in this study age group between 25-30 years, In regards with education majority of the responds were graduate 20(33%) ,majority of the responds were daily wages and majority of the responds were belongs to Muslim since that area is belongs to Muslim.

Table 2: Level of Knowledge on Preventing Mishaps at Home for their Children

Sl.No	Level of Knowledge	Pre Test		Post test		Chi square
		Number of respondents	Percentage	Number of respondents	Percentage	
1	Adequate	14	23.3	0	0	$\chi^2=120.50$ $p=0.001^* *$
2	Inadequate	31	51.7	0	0	
3	Moderate	15	25.0	21	35	
4	Good	0	0.0	39	65	

Figure 2: Level of Knowledge on Preventing Mishaps at Home for their Children

The above table shows that Pre -test and post -Test level of Knowledge prevention of accidents among mothers, before and after intervention 23.3% of women had appropriate knowledge prior to the structured interventional program, 51% had inadequate information, and 15% had moderate awareness about preventing accidents at home for their children following the interventional program. There is a favorable influence of educational approach

as evidenced by the fact that 21% of mothers had moderate knowledge on preventing disasters at home for their children, compared to 39% of respondents who had high knowledge. The significance was evaluated using the Chi square test. Thus, the researcher rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the research hypothesis.

Table 3: Comparison of Overall Knowledge Score Regarding Preventing Mishaps at Home for their Children

Sl.No	Test	Number of Mothers	Mean	SD	statistical paired t Test
1	Pre test	60	16.31	6.61	t=32.10 p=0.001*** Significant
2	Post test	60	31.08	4.93	

Note: Significant at P< 0.05**highly significant at P< 0.001

Figure 3: Comparison of Overall Knowledge Score Regarding Preventing Mishaps at Home for their Children

The overall knowledge score between the pretest and posttest is displayed in the above table. Generally speaking Mothers have an average mean score of 16.31 on the pretest and roughly 31.05 on the posttest. The pretest knowledge score varies significantly and is statistically significant. It indicates that they can answer

15 questions more correctly on the posttest than on the pretest. The paired t test was used to examine the differences.

Discussion

Regarding the sample's age distribution, of the 60 respondents, 19 (31.6%) of the mothers were in the age

range of 20 to 24 years, 21% were in the age range of 25 to 30 years, 16 (26.7%) were in the age range of 31 to 35 years, and 4 (6.7) were in the age range of over 36 years. Here, the researcher draws the conclusion that the majority of the study participants were between the ages of 25 and 30. Regarding education, the majority of respondents were graduates (20%), the majority reported daily wages, and the majority of respondents were Muslim since that region is home to Muslims.-from the results of pretest and the post test score were considerably less compared to posttest performances in all aspects of knowledge under preventing mishaps at home under the study .The findings showed that the enhancement of mean present score in found in the aspects of regarding prevention of mishaps among children's between the age group 0-5 years .

The pretest total knowledge mean score was 40.8% with a standard deviation of 6062%, and roughly 51.5 percent of respondents knew about definition and meaning mistakes at home. 37.9% knew the different kinds and reasons of accidents. 44% were familiar with first aid protocols. However, the posttest total knowledge mean score was shown to be 77.6% with a standard deviation of 4.99, indicating that almost 93.55 percent of respondents knew the definition and meaning of mishaps at home. Of those who knew about house accidents, 74.4% were aware of their causes, and 75.2% were aware of safety precautions and first aid protocols.

The mean and standard deviation of mothers' knowledge variables about preventing accidents in children aged 0 to 5 are compared. In the pretest, moms' mean score for overall knowledge level was 40.08 percent, with a standard deviation of roughly 6.62. The aforementioned data indicates that, in accordance with the investigator's previously acknowledged Research Hypothesis H1, there was a significant difference in mothers' knowledge about how to prevent accidents in children between the ages of 0 and 5 before and after educational approach intervention. The fact that the subjects' awareness of safety measures and first aid procedures for children at home significantly improved suggests that the educational interventional program that the investigator gave to all of the subjects was beneficial.

Recommendation

It is possible to compare moms in urban and rural areas' understanding of infant safety precautions through research. Many samples can be used to conduct the investigation. A study evaluating mothers' practices on child safety may be carried out periodically, an accident prevention study for primary school teachers might be carried out in different settings

Design and development of the program culturally appropriate content: ensure that the curriculum

reflects local customs and practices. Involve community leaders and mothers in the design process to improve relevance and acceptance. Interactive learning modules: include hands-on activities, demonstrations and role plays to facilitate better understanding and retention of safety practices.2. Targeted awareness and accessibility Different communication strategies: Use different channels (community centers, schools, health facilities) to reach mothers from different socio-economic backgrounds, ensuring inclusion. Flexible hours: Offering programs at various times, including evenings and weekends, to accommodate working mothers and other caregivers.3. Partnerships and collaborations Collaborate with local organizations: Create partnerships with NGOs, health services and educational institutions to leverage resources and expertise. Engage local experts: Engage child safety experts and health professionals to lead workshops, thereby improving credibility and knowledge transfer.

Conclusion

This study's findings indicate that moms' understanding of infant safety precautions was much enhanced by the organized instruction approach. Childhood accidents are a major concern. Children under the age of five are particularly vulnerable to injuries from home mishaps. The most frequent cause of injuries to children under five is falls. A mother's awareness of home accident prevention is crucial in reducing the risk of injuries in children. The study found that moms should receive greater education about preventing home accidents involving children under the age of five.

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